

An ORIGAMI Use-Case Validation via 6G-SANDBOX Experimentation

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Abstract—The transition to 6G presents many barriers to be overcome, as well as opportunities for innovation. The integration of Network Intelligence (NI) is pivotal in optimizing network performance, enhancing security, and improving resource allocation. The ORIGAMI project identifies 8 critical barriers towards 6G deployment, and proposes both architectural and NI innovations to overcome them. This paper discusses experimentation with one use-case that implements one such architectural innovation – namely, the Global Operator Model that leverages the Global Service-Based Architecture (GSBA). In particular, we focus on the use of the 6G-SANDBOX infrastructure to allow for proof-of-concept implementations of the GSBA. Overall, this paper serves as an example of how ORIGAMI’s approach to innovation benefits from state-of-the-art experimental platforms available via the 6G-SANDBOX project – thus highlighting the importance of joint architecture design and experimentation efforts.

Index Terms—6G, mobile network architectures, network intelligence, global mobile services, compute continuum

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition from 5G to 6G is not merely an incremental upgrade but a fundamental rethinking of how mobile networks are designed, operated, and trusted. Future networks are expected to support extreme heterogeneity in devices, services, and stakeholders, while simultaneously meeting stringent requirements on performance, security, sustainability, and automation. In this context, the ORIGAMI project [1], [2] analyzed the obstacles that hinder this vision, and identified eight concrete structural barriers in the successful evolution towards 6G: **(B1)** unsustainable virtualization of the RAN, **(B2)** limited interoperability across disaggregated RAN components, **(B3)** excessive latency in NI pipelines, **(B4)** under-exploited programmability in transport networks, **(B5)** the lack of globally exposed service APIs, **(B6)** an outdated trust model inherited from legacy architectures, **(B7)** insufficiently expressive representations of networking data, and **(B8)** excessive control-plane signaling overhead. These barriers are tightly coupled and cannot be addressed in isolation; instead, they demand holistic architectural solutions that integrate intelligence, security, and programmability across the entire network stack.

Towards removing these barriers, ORIGAMI proposes three architectural innovations: the **Compute Continuum Layer (CCL)**, which enables flexible placement of computation

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Fig. 1. Validation of the architecture envisioned by ORIGAMI through 6G-SANDBOX PoC.

from edge to cloud; the **Zero Trust Layer (ZTL)**, which redefines trust assumptions across administrative and technological boundaries; and the **Global Service-Based Architecture (GSBA)**, which extends service-based principles beyond the core network to enable cross-domain and cross-operator service exposure.

In this paper, we demonstrate the ORIGAMI methodology for validating the viability of these architectural components via proof-of-concept (PoC) implementations of the corresponding use-cases that specify them [1], as we show in Figure 1. Overall, ORIGAMI proposes a set of 21 use-cases that are explicitly linked to the three new architectural building blocks, ensuring alignment with ongoing standardization and international research efforts [2]. By grounding the use-case PoCs in concrete experimentation efforts (e.g., via testbed-driven efforts using platforms such as 6G-SANDBOX’s Malaga infrastructure), this work goes beyond conceptual design and provides tangible insights into how ORIGAMI’s innovations can be realized and evaluated in practice. In doing so, it contributes both empirical evidence and architectural guidance to ongoing discussions on the evolution of 6G systems.

In particular, in this paper we focus on the Global Mobile Network Operator (GMNO) use-case – tackling barriers B5 and B6 above, and implementing an operational model with global reach via the GSBA. Leveraging the **6G-SANDBOX**

project infrastructure, we build a proof-of-concept experiment that allows us to quantify the benefit of the GSBA towards achieving native-like performance for globally distributed end-users within the context of the GMNO. The GMNO builds upon the emerging concept of the Mobile Network Aggregator (MNA) – a disruptive type of player in the telco sector that provides global mobile connectivity [3]–[5]. The MNA operational model upgrades the Mobile Virtual Network Operator (MVNO) approach by leveraging the infrastructure of, not one (as traditional MVNOs do), but multiple base operators in different countries. To achieve this, MNAs overload the international roaming function, and benefit from the extensive global infrastructure that telcos have been shaping for decades.

Problem Formulation: In recent years, MNAs – such as Airalo [4] or emnify [5] – have emerged as a disruptive phenomenon in the telco sector to provide global mobile connectivity [3]. Their operational model upgrades the MVNO approach [6] by leveraging the infrastructure of multiple operators in different countries. Specifically, all MNAs gain access to (visited) Radio Access Networks (RANs) globally via interconnection through roaming hubs. The cellular ecosystem thus evolves in terms of complexity, with data paths that were once confined to a single operator realm now traversing multiple domains, and relying on resources from different entities (including the Visited MNO (v-MNO) as RAN provider, the Home MNO (h-MNO) as a roaming sponsor, the IP Packet eXchange (IPX) provider as interconnection fabric, and cloud service providers as network function hosts).

Despite this global interconnection, there is an intrinsic lack of trust between the h-MNO and the v-MNO, which fundamentally shapes how roaming is implemented and directly impacts communication performance. Specifically, the unwillingness of the h-MNO to expose charging and usage information to a foreign operator makes Home-Routed (HR) roaming the default roaming configuration [7], [8]. With HR roaming, all traffic is routed through the home country, regardless of the roaming user’s actual location. While this preserves control over charging and accounting, it also introduces a non-negligible delay and performance penalty [7], [8].

Consequently, MNAs still face significant challenges in offering a native-like service to their roaming end-users [4]. While their deployments demonstrate strong demand for seamless global connectivity, they also expose the limitations of the current 5G architecture. With our GMNO use-case, we argue that enabling truly global, native-like cellular connectivity requires rethinking roaming as a fundamental architectural problem. ORIGAMI’s GSBA delivers the global network architecture via which user traffic can be offloaded close to the point of access, while still ensuring trust, billing correctness, regulatory compliance, and service guarantees across operator boundaries.

ORIGAMI demonstrates this concept using the end-to-end validation environment of the **6G-SANDBOX** project. 6G-SANDBOX provides a large-scale experimentation infrastructure that integrates heterogeneous testbeds, compute and network resources, and AI/ML toolchains under a common

orchestration and exposure framework. Its design explicitly supports the co-creation, deployment and evaluation of 6G use cases across the compute-network continuum, enabling realistic experimentation with multi-domain, multi-stakeholder scenarios. By offering programmable access to RAN, transport, and core components, along with built-in support for data collection, experimentation automation, and KPI assessment, the platform serves as a critical enabler to validate NI-driven architectural concepts under operationally relevant conditions.

This paper is further structured as follows: In Section II we discuss the ORIGAMI architecture and the innovations that we introduce. In Section III we introduce the trial network concept that 6G-SANDBOX facilitates. In Section IV we discuss the ORIGAMI use-case that implements the GSBA/ZTL innovation and describe our experimentation with 6G-SANDBOX, and in Section V we conclude the paper.

II. ORIGAMI ARCHITECTURE INNOVATIONS

In this section, we give an overview of the three architectural advancements ORIGAMI proposes [2]. Then, we introduce the GMNO use-case that specifies the implementation of the component we further validate.

A. Architectural Building Blocks

The proposed architecture preserves the fundamental principles of 5G while preparing the ground for 6G systems, particularly by incorporating advanced Network Intelligence (NI) capabilities and enabling global-scale services. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the three principal components are the Compute Continuum Layer (CCL), the Zero-Trust Layer (ZTL), and the Global SBA (GSBA).

Global SBA (GSBA): The GSBA extends the service-based paradigm beyond its current 5G core boundaries to overcome fragmentation and siloed management across network domains such as the core network, orchestration systems, and the Radio Access Network (RAN). Instead of maintaining independent domain-specific interfaces, the GSBA introduces a unified service bus interconnecting these domains under a common architectural framework.

The GSBA integrates seamlessly with legacy 3GPP SBA mechanisms while supporting the CCL and ZTL innovations, enabling cross-domain orchestration, coordinated resource sharing, and enhanced trust management. A notable feature of the GSBA is its extension into the RAN domain, where traditionally monolithic components are decomposed into control-plane and user-plane functions, in a manner analogous to 5G core principles.

Applying SBA concepts within the RAN improves modularity, scalability, and automation capabilities. It enhances resilience, facilitates fine-grained programmability, and prepares the network for long-term technological evolution. By enabling consistent service exposure and coordination across domains, the GSBA contributes to a holistic, multi-domain management framework suited for future 6G systems.

Zero-Trust Layer (ZTL): The ZTL is conceived to establish a zero-trust interaction framework among entities participating in global service provisioning, while simultaneously

Fig. 2. Reference roaming configuration scenarios. The GMNO model extends the IPX hub breakout to place the UPF function as close as possible to the end-user, thus aiming to mimick LBO roaming performance.

addressing structural weaknesses in the traditional Mobile Network Operator (MNO) trust model.

With this, ORIGAMI introduces two fundamental transformations:

i) *Horizontal Exposure*. This dimension enables dynamic cooperation among operators, including new and non-traditional actors. It supports near real-time business interactions and financial settlement mechanisms, contrasting with current inter-operator clearing processes that rely on centralized Data Clearing Houses and involve long reconciliation cycles and delayed monetary flows.

ii) *Vertical Exposure*. This dimension empowers end-users with increased control over their connectivity. Unlike today’s model—where users are effectively bound to a single operator and provider switching remains operationally complex—the ZTL facilitates more flexible service relationships and reduces lock-in effects.

Together, these capabilities support a redefined trust framework aligned with both the internal optimization strategies of service providers and the evolving business logic of MNO ecosystems.

Compute Continuum Layer (CCL): The CCL is introduced as a key architectural mechanism to optimize network operation according to the characteristics of the underlying compute infrastructure. It abstracts heterogeneous computing resources through a CCL Broker and enables compute-aware lifecycle management of Network Functions (NFs) via a dedicated CCL Controller. This design allows dynamic allocation and orchestration of resources with the objective of improving energy efficiency and reducing Total Cost of Ownership (TCO).

The CCL is designed to accommodate a wide spectrum of computational technologies, including CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, SmartNICs, and other hardware accelerators. It is also extensible to emerging paradigms such as quantum computing platforms and programmable smart surfaces. By matching workload requirements to appropriate hardware accelerators, the CCL ensures that virtualized NFs can scale elastically while meeting stringent performance and latency constraints.

Fig. 3. GMNO interactions via ORIGAMI’s GSBA: the GMNO builds its service through agreements with base MNOs and CSPs; these latter interconnect via roaming hubs (i.e., IPX providers) to allow GMNO’s end-users global access to radio resources of visited MNOs.

B. ORIGAMI’s GMNO Use-Case

Building on ORIGAMI’s architectural innovations, the GMNO use-case rethinks how mobile connectivity is structured across administrative and geographic boundaries, with the goal of building truly global connectivity for cellular devices. Instead of relying on rigid bilateral roaming agreements and home-routed traffic anchoring, ORIGAMI introduces a logically unified abstraction that specifies the GSBA to operate above traditional MNO silos.

To understand why data plane placement is an important problem, consider the three roaming scenarios for the data breakout location, as shown in Figure 2. The Local Breakout (LBO) roaming scenario is what offers the native-like performance (i.e., similar to no roaming), while the Regional Breakout (RBO) and the Home Routed Roaming (HRR) scenarios translate into performance penalties. Specifically, with LBO, the data plane traffic exits the mobile network in the visited location, while with HRR, the data plane traffic exits the mobile network in the user’s home country. The latter is currently the preferred configuration by most Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) [7], [8]. HRR can cause significant performance penalties, especially if the user is roaming in a location geographically distant from their home location. A reasonable observation, given the limitations of home-routed roaming, would be to suggest that local-breakout roaming is used instead. However, local breakout suffers from policy issues which result in its actual real-world usage being effectively non-existent. As a way to tackle this, RBO allows the h-MNO to place their (home) User Plane Function (h-UPF) closer to the visited location, via IPX Hub Breakout locations. In ORIGAMI, we combine the policy advantages of home-routed roaming with the performance advantages of local-breakout. We achieve this by placing the home UPF not in the home location infrastructure, but in the visited location via third party infrastructure. This reduces the latency of the path between the visited UPF and the home UPF.

As Figure 3 depicts, the GMNO model abstracts mobile connectivity into a cross-domain, service-based architecture

Fig. 4. The 6G-SANDBOX experimentation framework.

where a global operator orchestrates connectivity across multiple independent MNOs. Instead of relying on bilateral roaming relationships, the GMNO leverages the Global Service-Based Architecture (GSBA) to expose standardized APIs across domains. h-MNOs and v-MNOs connect through IPX providers acting as trusted hubs, enabling secure signaling, data transport, and service exposure. Inter-operator agreements remain in place, but operational interaction is mediated through IPX hubs and global APIs, decoupling commercial relationships from real-time technical integration.

In this model, the GMNO integrates with multiple cloud service providers and IPX platforms to orchestrate global connectivity as a unified service layer. Base MNOs connect to IPX hubs, which interconnect with other IPX providers and onward to visited MNOs, creating a federated but logically unified ecosystem. Through GSBA, network capabilities (e.g., identity, policy, charging, exposure functions) can be programmatically accessed across domains, enabling seamless support for globally roaming users, IoT fleets, and digital nomads. The result is a scalable, cloud-integrated connectivity model where global service logic is centralized at the GMNO layer, while radio access and local network control remain distributed across visited operators. To validate the feasibility of the GSBA implementation via this use-case, we further leverage 6G-SANDBOX infrastructure, as we describe next.

III. 6G-SANDBOX FRAMEWORK

The 6G-SANDBOX experimentation facility has been selected for the ORIGAMI's GMNO use case validation, since it is one of the very few EU facilities designed to support technology and research validations as well as a wide range of measurements, covering almost any kind of network KPI that a third party might request.

The 6G-SANDBOX experimentation framework, depicted in Figure 4, enables the creation of end-to-end testing play-

grounds in the form of Trial Networks (TNs), i.e., fully configurable, manageable, and controllable network environments that integrate virtual, physical, and emulated resources. Trial Network instances can be tailored to specific network domains or technologies. Within the 6G-SANDBOX project, end-to-end TNs are offered by four experimentation platforms (network and compute infrastructures) in Athens, Malaga, Berlin and Oulu. Going beyond current approaches, 6G-SANDBOX maximizes replicability and reusability by releasing its entire software suite as open source through the 6G-SANDBOX Toolkit, allowing any experimentation platform to become TN-ready. The TN software components are maintained in a shared repository; the 6G-Library, which allows experimenters to automatically and modularly deploy a TN by selecting the required components on demand.

For the GMNO use case, the Malaga platform was interconnected with the ORIGAMI infrastructure. An innovative experimentation approach followed (see Figure 4) composed of three main planes:

- The User/Control Plane, managing the interactions, connections, and data transmission among the network components;
- The Experimentation Plane, facilitating the design, execution, and monitoring of experiments; and
- The Trial Network Plane, handling the deployment and configuration of TN and managing the resources of each TN as well as the interfaces towards the TN users.

IV. GMNO PROOF OF CONCEPT

The GMNO use-case leverages the GSBA architectural innovations to enhance the geospatial granularity of breakout locations [5] by exploiting cloud architectures, thus potentially achieving performance similar to that of a native operator in the end-user location [3]. A major goal of this use-case is to enable a global operator with local-like performance. The

Fig. 5. Latency varies significantly depending on the breakout location and the local (visited) network. This figure extends the 9-month analysis introduced in [9] with an additional 7 months of GTP ping latency measurements from seven potential breakout locations within the tested public cloud infrastructure.

”global operator” part of this will still be achieved through roaming, while the local-like performance will be achieved through careful data plane placement. With this attempt, we aim to explore how far we can push the international roaming setup currently exploited by global aggregators.

A. Performance Baseline

For the GMNO PoC, ORIGAMI leverages the GSBA for flexible, migratory deployment of the UPF, thus defining the mobile user plane across global infrastructure, including that offered by third parties such as trusted cloud providers. In this section, we introduce the experimental setup towards validating this elastic design via the 6G-SANDBOX platform, focusing on realistic mobile cloud-continuum scenarios.

In the context of building a fluid global footprint, the h-MNO must control the traffic breakout region to maintain compatibility with cellular ecosystem’s zero-trust model between h-MNO, v-MNO, and third-party infrastructure providers. While local breakout offers optimal user experience, it’s architecturally incompatible with this zero-trust requirement.

To capture the baseline for the GMNO ORIGAMI design, we measure the latency from seven fixed regional breakout locations via public cloud infrastructure (namely, in Brazil, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Singapore, Switzerland and USA) to the infrastructure of multiple local (visited) networks. Figure 5 quantifies the Round Trip Time (RTT) impact of seven different breakout regions using GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP) echo measurements, introduced in [9], demonstrating the latency advantages of regional (or local) breakout that must

be balanced against the trust and control constraints imposed by ORIGAMI’s zero-trust architecture.

Specifically, we conduct active measurements of IPX latency, defined as the RTT between a visited network’s Serving Gateway (SGW) and a home network’s Packet Data Network Gateway (PGW) across six continents. Note that, while we perform these baseline measurements leveraging access to a 4G-only MNA, they offer valuable real-world insights into the current performance of these providers. Our setup utilizes breakouts in the seven aforementioned regions connected via multiple IPX carriers and peering points, where each measurement is characterized by the target SGW and source PGW. By employing periodic GTP-C and GTP-U echo requests, we maintain continuous observations while mitigating transient network bias. Although these measurements utilize LTE infrastructure, the underlying IPX interconnection remains identical for 5G — with UPF instances replacing SGW and PGW functions — ensuring our findings remain valid for 5G and beyond roaming.

In particular, we observe that latencies corresponding to users in Spain (i.e., towards an SGW in Spain) from the Ireland breakout location (pentagon-marked location in Figure 5) are on average the order of ≈ 50 ms. We argue that the elastic deployment of the breakout location closer to the actual location of the end-user improves the latency contribution of the interconnection tunnel between the v-MNO location and the RBO location.

Fig. 6. ORIGAMI deployment within the 6G-SANDBOX experimental infrastructure: we deploy a Trial Network that allows us to capture the benefit of a flexible data plane, with breakout locations (i.e., GMNO UPF) closer to the (visited) end-user location.

B. 6G-SANDBOX Trial Network

The ORIGAMI evaluation aims to demonstrate how the GMNO mechanisms support dynamic placement and relocation of user-plane functions, while maintaining end-to-end service continuity. Particular emphasis is placed on: (i) showcasing the elastic user-plane deployment across distributed edge and regional sites, and (ii) assessing integration with state-of-the-art cloud-native and telco tooling available in the 6G-SANDBOX experimental testbed.

We execute the experimental campaign on a dedicated trial network instantiated over the 6G-SANDBOX Málaga infrastructure (i.e. the Victoria network¹), complemented with remote resources in a public cloud region. This region is an AWS Outpost deployment in the Victoria network, physically hosted in Málaga, and logically mapped to the AWS Paris region. The trial topology includes a local Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) in Málaga, interconnected via Transit Gateways with VPCs in Paris and Ireland, enabling a multi-region mobile core and user-plane deployment.

Figure 6 shows the detailed experimental setup that we designed specifically for GMNO validation. We leverage the technology stack available in 6G-SANDBOX to manage the Trial Network deployment, as follows:

- RAN emulation: UERANSIM-based gNB and UE;
- Core network: Open5GS-based EPC/5GC stack;
- Control-plane functions: hosted in Ireland (home region);
- User-plane functions (UPF): dynamically deployable in Ireland or Málaga (mapped to the Ireland AWS region);
- Orchestration: Kubernetes-based container deployment;
- Interconnection: AWS Transit Gateway and production-grade IP connectivity;
- Infrastructure: AWS Outposts (edge) + AWS Regions (regional/home cloud).

With this, we emulate the following scenario: an end-user with a SIM card sponsored by an h-MNO from Ireland travels to Spain. For this user, we compare two data plane configurations that are enabled by the GMNO model:

- **“baseline” scenario:** breakout hosted in the Ireland VPC, co-located with the h-MNO core (Open5GS deployment in AWS). This corresponds to a classical home-routed roaming configuration, where user-plane traffic is tunneled back to the home country before Internet breakout.
- **“near-breakout” scenario:** leveraging the multi-region (Ireland - Paris) kubernetes cluster, the breakout location is physically hosted in the edge cloud deployment in Málaga, part of the 6G-SANDBOX infrastructure; this emulates the RBO scenario that aims to map the breakout location as close as possible to the visited end-user loca-

¹<https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/malaga/>

tion, effectively approximating a local breakout scenario.

In this configuration, the cellular network operators is also a large ISP that directly peer with public clouds in multiple locations; in our case, we assume the direct peering in Málaga between the 5G and the corresponding cloud infrastructure provider. Not only do we expect 5G traffic to flow over direct connections, we expect 5G cloudification to spur operators to increase the quantity of peering. This translates into an important implication for the GMNO: the well-known anomalies of BGP in the wild—such as policy-driven detours through intermediate Autonomous Systems (ASes) are largely mitigated. In the GMNO setting, intermediate AS policy enforcement does not arbitrarily shape end-to-end paths between source and destination domains. As a result, the data-plane latency approaches that of the local breakout ideal, while preserving the operational and commercial interconnection framework of the IPX network. Indeed, our measurements confirm that in the GMNO baseline setup the latency is ≈ 30 ms on average, which is consistent with wide-area home-routed roaming measurements observed in production environments in Figure 5. This further drops by two orders of magnitude to ≈ 0.5 ms on average for the GMNO “near-breakout” scenario. This validates that ORIGAMI’s GMNO elastic user-plane placement achieves performance characteristics approaching those of local breakout, while maintaining the trust and commercial stability of home-routed roaming.

V. CONCLUSION

The ORIGAMI project introduces three key architectural advances – namely the Compute Continuum Layer (CCL), the Zero Trust Layer (ZTL), and the Global Service-Based Architecture (GSBA) – whose implementation responds to the existing limitations of the current 5G system architecture. In particular, the ORIGAMI project identified eight critical barriers to overcome towards the deployment of 6G, and different use cases enable the design and implementation of the key innovation components. In this paper, we focused on the validation of one specific use-case – the Global Mobile Network Operator (GMNO) model – leveraging the GSBA. We discussed the implementation of the GSBA through the GMNO use-case, leveraging the experimental infrastructure

of 6G-SANDBOX. We showed the successful definition of a 6G-SANDBOX Trial Network dedicated for experimentation with the flexible GMNO data plane. Our results validate a reduction of two orders of magnitude in the latency of an end-user connecting to the GMNO.

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